

**Fairness & Wellbeing
Commission**

Session 3: Working Age Data

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Population

In Doncaster, the population size has increased by 1.9%, from around 302,400 in 2011 to 308,700 in 2021. This is lower than the overall increase for England (6.6%).

At 1.9%, Doncaster's population increase is lower than the increase for Yorkshire and The Humber (3.7%).

Population change (%) by age group in Doncaster, 2011 to 2021

- decrease in people aged 15 to 64 years
- 62% of Doncaster residents are aged 16-64
- **191,300** working age residents (16-64)

Ethnic diversity in Doncaster has increased; the 2021 Census shows that the Doncaster population was 86.6% White British compared with 96.5% in 2001.

The percentage of the population in ethnic minority groups

The level of diversity varies across the City; 49.5% of the population of Doncaster Centre and Hyde park identify as White British compared with 96.8% of residents in Cadeby, Hickleton and Hampole

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Language

92.76% of people in Doncaster speak English as their main language

The most common languages spoken by Doncaster residents after English
(Census 2021)

Polish	2.18%
Romanian	1.82%
Kurdish	0.23%
Slovak	0.23%
Turkish	0.21%
Lithuanian	0.18%
Arabic	0.17%
Nepalese	0.17%
Urdu	0.16%
Russian	0.15%
Latvian	0.15%
Bulgarian	0.14%
Punjabi	0.14%

5.1% - 6,800 Households in Doncaster have no members that speak English

This is an increase from 2.6% in 2011

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Disability & Unpaid Care

Doncaster has 62,418 people living with a disability or long term health condition

20.4% Doncaster, 17.8% Nationally

Residents disabled under the Equality Act whose day-to-day activities were:

Limited a little

33,422

Limited a lot

28,996

47,375

Over a third of Doncaster households have at least one person who is disabled under the Equality Act

The Equality Act defines an individual as disabled if they have a physical or mental impairment that has a substantial and long-term negative effect on their ability to carry out normal day-to-day activities.

An unpaid carer may look after, give help or support to anyone who has long-term physical or mental ill-health conditions, illness or problems related to old age.

Weekly hours of unpaid care provided in Doncaster:

1-19 hrs 11,845

20-49 hrs 6,468

50+ hrs 9,819

There are 28,132 people in Doncaster providing regular unpaid care

9.5% Doncaster residents

Median income: £25,356

which was growth on only 1.9% on the previous year

In 2021, the median gross weekly earnings for men in Doncaster were £585, compared to £349 for women.

This represents the largest gender pay gap of across South Yorkshire.

Weekly Gross Pay (Median)

the median hourly pay for white workers in Doncaster in 2020 was £12.00, compared to £10.35 for BAME workers, representing an ethnicity pay gap of 13.8%.

27,000 Doncaster residents earned less than the Real Living Wage in 2021

Income deprivation in Doncaster

In **Doncaster**, **16.6%** of the population was income-deprived in 2019. Of the 316 local authorities in England (excluding the Isles of Scilly), Doncaster is ranked **48th most income-deprived**.

Doncaster

More income deprived profile

Of the 194 neighbourhoods in Doncaster, 68 were among the 20% most income deprived in England

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Debt

According to data from the Money Advice Service, in 2020, Doncaster was ranked as the 11th most indebted local authority area in the UK, with an average debt per adult of £1,174.

Total number of individual insolvencies (2022) for Doncaster & Doncaster CIPFA nearest neighbours

Debt was the single biggest issue for which Doncaster residents sought assistance from Citizen's Advice this year

data from Creditfix, shows that average debt levels in Doncaster have increased by 7.6% between January and March of this year

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Education, Skills & Training

IMD 2019 Score - Education, Skills and Training Decile

This measures the lack of attainment and skills in the local population.

Doncaster is 3rd most deprived out of 151 Upper-tier local authorities for Education, Skills and Training

Highest level of Qualification	Doncaster (count of residents 16+)	Doncaster %	Yorkshire & Humber %	England %
None	61,805	24.6%	20.6	18.1
Level 1 and entry level	28,721	11.4%	10.1	9.7
Level 2	37,907	15.1%	13.6	13.3
Apprenticeship	16,765	6.7%	6.1	5.3
Level 3	41,594	16.6%	17.4	16.9
Level 4	56,931	22.7%	29.5	33.9
Other	7,205	2.9%	2.6	2.8

Job Related Training Percentage

The employment rate in Doncaster in 2021 was 70.1%, which was slightly below the national average.

Number of hours worked Per week
(of Doncaster residents in employment)

% in employment who are self employed
Total age 16+

Industry

	Doncaster Local Authority	
	count	%
All usual residents aged 16 years and over in employment the week before the census	137,859	100.0
A: Agriculture, Forestry and fishing	800	0.6
B: Mining and quarrying	187	0.1
C: Manufacturing	12,396	9.0
D: Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	878	0.6
E: Water supply; Sewerage, Waste management and Remediation activities	1,197	0.9
F: Construction	14,655	10.6
G: Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	29,090	21.1
H: Transport and storage	11,402	8.3
I: Accommodation and food service activities	5,721	4.1
J: Information and communication	3,192	2.3
K: Financial and insurance activities	2,957	2.1
L: Real estate activities	1,210	0.9
M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	4,387	3.2
N: Administrative and support service activities	6,431	4.7
O: Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	7,672	5.6
P: Education	10,744	7.8
Q: Human health and social work activities	20,210	14.7
R, S, T, U Other	4,730	3.4

Deindustrialisation

A significant proportion of work in Doncaster in the mid 20th century was in mining and manufacturing. Doncaster experienced large-scale job losses in the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s owing to industrial decline. The main labour market response was not an increase in unemployment; instead workers withdrew into economic inactivity. The impact of this is still visible today.

Involuntary inactivity, 1981 to 2022

Many post-industrial cities, particularly in the North, have not transitioned towards high-skilled, high-wage economies. Instead, they have replicated the low-skilled nature of their economies. As a result, some places have not only lost jobs in mining and manufacturing, which were relatively well-paid, but the jobs that have subsequently been created are disproportionately lower skilled and lower paid in workplaces like distribution sheds and call centres. It has meant that deindustrialised cities such as Doncaster have been stuck in a low-skill, low-wage equilibrium.

This Graph shows the impact of deindustrialisation on subsequent generations – the children and grandchildren of those withdrawing from the labour market in the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s.

16,800 (17.7%)

Number of workless households

Households where no-one aged 16 or over is in employment.

Y&H 14.3%, UK 14%

Economically Inactive by Reason Total Split

29,000
Doncaster
Residents
aged 16+ have
never worked
or are long
term
unemployed
(Census 2021)

Inactivity due to sickness, 1981 and 2022

Usual residents aged 16 years and over who were economically inactive, 2021, Doncaster

Economic Inactivity

% of Doncaster Residents aged 16+ that are not currently in Employment that...

Have Never worked 27.2%

Have not worked in the last 12 months 61.6%

Worked in the last 12 months 11.2%

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Benefits claimants

Percentage of Working Age Population Claimants in Doncaster by Age Band

Percentage of Working Age Population Claimants by Area

Percentage Working Age Pop Claimants by Ward

The areas which have the highest rates are concentrated in the centre of Doncaster, in areas such as Balby, Hexthorpe and Town Ward. The lowest rates are seen in areas with typically older or more well off populations such as Sprotborough, Edenthorpe & Kirk Sandall

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Employment Opportunities

Industries with the largest *change in job postings* since 2020 are more likely to be rurally located.

Residents age 17-25 per km² by LSOA

% users within 15 minutes of
employment centres with at
least 5000 jobs available by
PT/walk 2019 %

53

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Transport

35,102 Doncaster Residents (27.8%) of households do not have access to a car or van

% Households that do not have access to a car or Van by MSOA

Central Doncaster & Hyde Park	49.8%	Armthorpe North	22.4%
Hexthorpe & Balby North	43.6%	Scawthorpe	21.5%
Conisbrough North	36.3%	Hatfield West	20.6%
Belle Vue & Town Fields	35.6%	Askern, Campsall & Norton	20.3%
Bentley & Toll bar	35.2%	Warmsworth, Braithwell & Stainton	18.6%
Mexborough West	32.3%	Edenthorpe & Mere Lane	17.8%
Intake	30.9%	Armthorpe South	17.1%
Edlington	29%	Cusworth	17%
New Rossington	28.6%	Bessacarr & Bawtry Road	15.7%
Stainforth	27.8%	Kirk Sandall & Barnby Dun	15.6%
Mexborough East	27.5%	Rossington	14.2%
Bentley Rise	27.4%	Cadeby, Hickleton & Hampole	13.9%
Cantley Park	27.1%	Tickhill	13.2%
Carcroft	27%	Hatfield East	13%
Wheatley Hills	26.1%	Sprotbrough	12.8%
Conisbrough South	25.6%	Bawtry, Austerfield & Hayfield	12.2%
Adwick Le Street & Woodlands	24.3%	Bessacarr Grange & Lakeside	11%
Thorne	24%	Old Cantley, Auckley & Finningley	9.4%
Moorends	22.4%		

Public Transport

- Doncaster has a hub and spoke style public transport system; the majority of bus routes start or end in the town centre.
- Travel between outer areas of the borough can be lengthy e.g. travel between Askern and Thorne can be over 2 hours
- Bus timetables often do not support working hours

Method of Travel to work by Doncaster Residents (Census 2021)

Car or Van (driver)	57.9%
Car or Van (Passenger)	6.7%
Bus/minibus/coach	4.6%
Train	0.8%
Bicycle	1.8%
On foot	7.1%
Motorcycle/Scooter/Moped	0.3%
Taxi	1.1%
Work Mainly from Home	18.5%

Distance travelled to work by Doncaster Residents (Census 2021)

Under 10km	41.7%
10-30km	18.2%
More than 30 Km	5.2%
Working from Home	18.5%

In 2020 - 10% of adults across Doncaster, Barnsley and Rotherham had either never used the internet or had not used the internet within the last 3 months
an estimated 24,500 Doncaster residents

Nationally 21% of internet users only use a smartphone to go online

Internet users who **ONLY** use a smartphone to go online

Reasons people gave for not being online:

- 37% say they don't have the right equipment
- 36% say it is too expensive for them
- 42% say they are not interested - 'it isn't for me'
- 46% say it is too complicated

Compared to extensive users, people who are 'limited users' are around:

- 4 times more likely to be from **low income households**
- 1.5 times more likely to be from **BAME groups**

A third of internet users were unaware of the potential for inaccurate or biased information online; 6% of internet users believed that all the information they find online is truthful and 30% of internet users don't know – or don't think about – whether the information they find is truthful or not

Private Sector Rent within 3 miles of the centre of Doncaster

No of beds	LHA Rate (PW)	LHA Rate (PCM)	Average Rent 19/5/23	Median Rent 19/5/23
One Bedroom	£86.30	£373.97	£589	£550
Two Bedroom	£101.26	£438.79	£662	£650
Three Bedroom	£111.62	£483.69	£885	£838
Four Bedroom	£150.74	£653.21	£1272	£1275

Accommodation type	Doncaster Count	Doncaster %	Y&H %	England %
Detached	32,223	24.1	21.6	22.9
Semi-detached	60,700	45.5	37.6	31.5
Terraced	28,207	21.1	26.1	23
In a purpose built block of flats or tenement	8,534	6.4	11.1	17.1
Part of a converted or shared house inc. bedsits	1,670	1.3	1.7	3.5
Part of another converted building e.g. former school/church/warehouse	455	0.3	0.9	0.8
In a commercial building, e.g. office building/hotel/above a shop	842	0.6	0.7	0.8
Caravan or other mobile or temporary structure	849	0.6	0.2	0.4

Percentage of households by housing tenure, **Doncaster**

Doncaster has 133,480 households

One - person households	41,667
Single family households	85,449
Other	6,312

Semi-detached property prices in Doncaster

Typical payments on a 5 year fixed mortgage for an average semi-detached property in **Doncaster** is **£862** with a deposit of £15,000 and a 25 year mortgage.

The average price for a semi-detached property in Doncaster is £157k in Feb 2023.

This has increased by **34%** since Feb 2018.

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Commercial determinants – Diet and Exercise

8% worse than national average

59%

of Doncaster residents are **physically active**

-7% worse than national average

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19.6 per cent of people aged over 18 in Doncaster were smokers in 2021, up slightly from 19.4 per cent the year before.

The Proportion of Current Smokers Aged 18+ by Local Authority, UK (%)

Smoking prevalence is much higher amongst the following groups:

- People living in rented accommodation
- People in routine manual Jobs
- People who reported having no qualifications
- People in receipt of benefits
- People who have a health condition which severely limits their activity

People living in the most deprived areas are more than **four times more likely to smoke** than those living in the least deprived areas.

Commercial Determinants – Alcohol & Tobacco

In Doncaster, alcohol use and harm are particularly concentrated in areas of deprivation, with higher rates of alcohol-related hospital admissions, mortality, and crime in the most deprived areas.

74% (three quarters) of all admissions related to alcohol involve people from areas within the most deprived 40% of Doncaster

Admission episodes for alcohol-related conditions - narrow definition

It is estimated that Doncaster has around 4,313 dependent drinkers and 3,848 hospital admissions caused by alcohol each year.

Commercial Determinants - Gambling

In Doncaster there are 58 registered betting premises.
This includes betting shops, bingo halls, tracks & adult gaming centres (as of January 2022)

Betting shops are cited in Doncaster's more deprived areas.

- at-risk and problem gamblers are more typically male & in younger age groups.
- there is a higher prevalence of at-risk and problem gambling among people with poor health, low life satisfaction and wellbeing.
- Links to **increased alcohol consumption**.
- Risk factors for subsequent harmful gambling among **children and young people**:
 - impulsivity,
 - substance use (alcohol, tobacco & illegal drugs)
 - being male
 - depression.
- Deaths from **suicide** were significantly higher among adults with gambling disorder or problems
- **Crime** - including theft, selling drugs, taking out loans in other people's names, stealing from friends and family and committing fraud to fund problem gambling.
- Links to **job loss and poor performance**.
- Gambling-related debt was identified as a crucial harm that can lead to other harms such as relationship problems, physical and mental health problems, and crime.
- Gambling directly causes **relationship problems** affecting the gambler and their close associates, including their children.
- Around 7% of the population of Great Britain (adults and children) were found to be **negatively affected by someone else's gambling**

1294 problem gamblers and **9832** at risk gamblers in Doncaster. Based on ONS population projections for 2021 in Doncaster (age 15+)

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Mental Health & Wellbeing

7% **low levels of satisfaction**
worse than national average

9% **low levels of happiness**
similar to national average

5% **low feelings of worthwhile**
worse than national average

Average Measure of Personal Well-Being
Rating of Happiness (ONS)

The prevalence of common mental health problems by employment status

Employment status is linked to mental health outcomes, with unemployed or economically inactive having higher rates of common mental health problems than those employed.

Employment is generally beneficial for mental health. However, the mental health benefits of employment depend on the quality of work; work that is low-paid, insecure or poses health risks can be damaging to mental health.

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Crime & Violence

Crime Types description

for the last 3 years (Nov 2019-Sep 2020)

Proportion of Crime with a Domestic Abuse flag

In the year ending March 2021, there were **2,958** recorded violent offenses in Doncaster, representing a rate of **10.4 per 1,000 population** compared to the national average of 6.3 per 1,000 population.

Admissions to hospital for violent crime

67.5 per 100,000 in Doncaster

41.9 Nationally

47.3 Regionally